

THEORETICAL ISSUES ON THE FORMATION OF THE ECONOMIC THINKING OF YOUTH

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Annotation: In this article, transition to the third stage of the renaissance in our country during globalization, building a legal-democratic state based on market relations and forming the foundations of civil society, the issue of economic thinking of young people is given special importance.

Keywords: country, economy, property, youth, outlook, thinking, country, goal.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье переход к третьему этапу возрождения в нашей стране в условиях глобализации, построения правового-демократического государства, основанного на рыночных отношениях и формирования основ гражданского общества, вопросу экономического мышления молодежи уделяется особое значение.

Ключевые слова: страна, экономика, собственность, молодежь, мировоззрение, мышление, страна, цель.

ЁШЛАРНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ ТАФАККУРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШГА ДОИР НАЗАРИЙ МАСАЛАЛАР

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Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада глобаллашув даврида мамлакатимизда учинчи ренессанс босқичига ўтиш, бозор муносабатларига асосланган ҳуқуқий-демократик давлатни қуриш ва фуқаролик жамияти асосларини шакллантириш жараёнида ёшларнинг иқтисодий тафаккурини шакллантириш масаласи алоҳида аҳамият берилган.

Калит сўзлар: мамлакат, иқтисодиёт, мулк, ёшлар, дунёқараш, тафаккур, мамлакат, мақсад.

In today's globalization era, transition to the third stage of renaissance in our country, building a legal-democratic state based on market relations and forming the foundations of civil society, the question of forming the economic thinking of young people is of particular importance. After all, one of the original goals of the reforms in the socio-economic sphere carried out in our country is aimed at the same issue.

Since the first years of independence, due to the emergence of a market economy based on diverse ownership as a result of the expropriation of property in Uzbekistan, a new socio-philosophical worldview and an economic worldview began to form in the minds of our youth. In particular, the growing sense of ownership of the economy has led to the emergence of a new economic way of thinking in the daily life of young people. This is based on a deep understanding of the content and nature of the economic reforms taking place inside the country, establishing economic relations with far and near neighbors, and also thinking philosophically about the new economy emerging in the process of globalization, as well as about strategic problems such as taking a unique place in the world economic space. also created a possibility. In our country, in the new era, that is, in the period of the third renaissance, our youth, whose economic thinking is developing, is the force that turns this opportunity into reality. Therefore, in this chapter, we tried to reveal the theoretical-philosophical aspects of the issues of socio-philosophical analysis of the development of the economic thinking of young people using the methods of historicity and logic, analysis and synthesis, and systematicity. Ensuring economic well-being in the society, raising the human factor, further increasing the meaningfulness of work, improving the spirituality of young people, who are the subjects of activity, largely depends on the level of their economic culture and thinking. The first president of our country I. Karimov noted, "the goals and tasks we have set before ourselves in terms of modernization of the country and creation of decent living conditions for the population, as well as the changes taking place in the regional and world markets, strong demand and competition make the deepening of economic reforms an objective condition".[1]

The general laws on which the socio-economic basis of society is based influence the formation of economic thinking and decision-making. We try to express and justify our point of view, following the conceptual rule of "affects". The emergence and development of the economic thinking of young people during the new stage of development in Uzbekistan, that is, during the "Third Renaissance", is an objective socio-economic process. That is why the philosophical study of the development of "economic thinking" requires the analysis of such concepts as "economic consciousness", "economic relations", "economic culture", "economic development" and revealing their essence.

In this process, one of the most urgent tasks is to form a new economic mindset in young people, change their worldview, and create an opportunity for them to independently define their own work fields and forms. After all, in the conditions of economic globalization, moreover, in the period of transition to the "Third Renaissance", in order to deeply understand the essence of today's trends, studying them in connection with the economic and spiritual life and culture of the society acquires important scientific-theoretical and practical importance.[2] In these realities, young people are encouraged to rely on their creative initiative and entrepreneurship, their strength and potential, their effective economic activity is supported, and of course, production is subordinated to their interests. In such conditions, economic, spiritual and cultural factors and social norms are reflected in the activities of social structures such as planning, supply, market, finance, and strengthening the economic status of young people in society.

The market economy requires initiative, efficiency, high entrepreneurship. But these qualities cannot be determined in young people who have not developed economic thinking. Human spirituality ensures his economic activity, besides, the development of economic thinking is the main requirement of the market economy. That's why in every era, the economic thinking of young people, the problem of harmony of material and spiritual factors in it, researching from a socio-philosophical point of view is gaining important theoretical and practical importance.

The question of economy and the relations related to it have been of interest to scientists since ancient times, and many Eastern and Western thinkers have expressed their opinions about it. Since it is not within the task of our research to study all of them historically, we considered it appropriate to philosophically analyze the opinions expressed in the literature published in our country at the end of the 20th century and up to the present day of the 21st century, especially during the "Third Renaissance".[3]

When economists assess the issue of "economy", they consider it as a unique form of human relations aimed at economic change and mastering of life activities that have been going on since the beginning of human existence on earth. Therefore, the economy is embodied in the minds of people as a certain process. There are also views on economic thinking as a form of thinking that regulates economic and property, legal relations between people.

Economic thinking is explained as a primary and secondary reality - if as a primary reality it is a product of the intelligence given to man by God, then as a secondary thinking it is a form of thinking that has arisen in the economic activities of people and is aimed at understanding economic relations. Depending on how developed their economic thinking is, the position of young people in the economic life of society, or rather their social status, is formed. As a logical confirmation of the above ideas, the economist L.S. Blyakhman explains economic thinking as "the process of reflection of economic relations in the human mind, assimilation of economic knowledge by them, and the process of economic activity becoming invisible in their mind."[4]

Taking the definitions given by the science of philosophy to the concept of social consciousness as a methodological basis, the concept of economic thinking can be defined as follows, relying on the valuable opinions of the above-mentioned scientists. Economic thinking is one of the forms of social consciousness, and it is the passion, feelings, ideas, ideals, views, thoughts and theories aimed at feeling, intellectually understanding the material and spiritual life of the existing society, especially the economic relations between people, and changing them in the future. is a unique integrated system. It is clear from this definition that economic thinking includes aspects of emotional (emotional) cognition and mental thinking. Economic thinking has a special role in this. In short, first of all, the views on social life and changes in consciousness in Eastern philosophy serve as an important spiritual heritage, value in deepening the understanding that the implementation of social changes in our lives today is related to economic consciousness. [5] At this point, the question of forming and developing the economic thinking of young people, who are active successors of society, is of great importance. In general, economic thinking is manifested in the following qualities of young people:

- the process of understanding economic categories and laws by young people and the form of their implementation through laws;
 - to exist on the basis of economic relations in society
- the extent to which young people understood the concepts and conclusions;
- the ability of young people to acquire economic knowledge and use it effectively;
 - which cannot be known directly through intuition, perception and imagination the conscious manifestation of phenomena that reflect the economic process and relations in the thinking of young people.

In the action strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, in the concepts of national economy development of the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, and other draft laws, opportunities were created to encourage the implementation of this rule. Today, as we are concerned about the economic progress of our country and its further development, we should teach not only the adults, but also our youth, who are the successors of the third renaissance, to master the economic teachings of the above thinkers.[5]

In turn, the structural structure of economic thinking will look like this: each of these structures acquires a separate meaning. Firstly, the understanding of the nature of economic activity, that is, having primary information about the economic activity carried out by young people, serves as a starting point for his further activity; secondly, it is required to acquire generalized information about the reflection, types and laws of social production, that is, each subject can choose his own type and form of activity and have information in this field; thirdly, young people can turn theoretical ideas into practical actions and apply economic thinking to their activities.

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